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1 **Genetic variation in chicken interferon signalling pathway genes in research**
2 **lines showing differential viral resistance**

3

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22 **Running title:** Variation in chicken interferon signalling genes

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27 **Abstract**

28 Avian viruses of economic interest are a significant burden on the poultry industry,
29 affecting production traits and resulting in mortality. Furthermore, zoonosis of avian viruses
30 risks pandemics developing in humans. Vaccination is the most common method of controlling
31 viruses; however current vaccines often lack cross protection against multiple strains of each
32 virus. The mutagenicity of these viruses has also led to virulent strains emerging that can
33 overcome the protection offered by vaccines. Breeding chickens with a more robust innate
34 immune response may help in tackling current and emerging viruses. Understanding the genetic
35 evolution of different lines will thus provide a useful tool in helping the host in the fight against
36 pathogens. This study focuses on the interferon genes and their receptors in different chicken
37 lines that are known to be more resistant or susceptible to particular avian viruses. Comparing
38 genotypic differences in these core immune genes between the chicken lines may explain
39 phenotypic differences observed and aid the identification of causative variations. The relative
40 resistance/susceptibility of each line to viruses of interest (Marek's disease virus, infectious
41 bursal disease, infectious bronchitis virus and avian influenza virus) has previously been
42 determined. Here we identify single nucleotide polymorphisms in interferons and downstream
43 genes. Functional prediction tools were used to identify variants that may be affecting protein
44 structure, mRNA secondary structure or transcription factor and micro-RNA binding sites.
45 These variants were then considered in the context of the **research** lines and their distribution
46 between phenotypes. **We highlight 60 variants of interest in the interferon pathway genes that**
47 **may account for susceptibility/resistance to viral pathogens.**

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51

52 **Introduction**

53 Study of the innate immune system is important as it is seen as a generalised first line of
54 defence and a step in the initiation of immune responses to a pathogen. Induction of the interferon
55 (IFN) signalling pathway is central to this response. The IFN system in chickens is of particular
56 interest as it bears many similarities to the human system, but its simplified nature makes it an
57 ideal model for studying this system. The interferon response in chickens is induced by pattern
58 recognition receptors (PRRs) that react to pathogenic materials such as viral RNA, and this causes
59 a signal cascade resulting in the upregulation of the type I (*IFN α* , *IFN β* , *IFN κ*), type II (*IFN γ*)
60 and type III (*IFN λ*) interferon genes. Once produced, these interferons can induce an antiviral
61 state by interacting with complementary receptor complexes as detailed in **Figure 1** [1,2].

62 In **vertebrate species**, it was initially believed that type I and III interferons were redundant
63 due to the similarity in signal cascade and interferon stimulated genes (ISGs) affected. However,
64 whilst type I receptors are expressed in most cells, the *IL-28R α* (*IFNLRI*) receptor appears to be
65 preferentially expressed in specific cells such as epithelial cells. This suggests that the type I
66 system works in a more systemic fashion compared to the cell-specific type III interferon system
67 [2,3]. Furthermore, inducing expression of *IFNLRI* in **chicken** fibroblasts allows IFN λ to induce
68 the type III antiviral response, further supporting the view that the distribution of this receptor
69 determines antiviral response in these cells [4]. The type II IFN system **in vertebrate species** is
70 unique by comparison as its function is predominantly restricted to immune cells and IFN γ is
71 principally produced by natural killer cells [5]. Despite the overlap between the systems
72 highlighted in **Figure 1**, it is evident the interferon systems **play a distinct role in vertebrate**
73 **species.**

74 The economic impact of avian viruses on the poultry industry cannot be **overstated**.
75 Infections can result in a reduction in egg production, condemnation of consumable meat,
76 immunosuppression leading to secondary infections and mortality. In the context of this study,

77 we will focus on resistance to four economically important viruses: Marek's disease virus (MDV)
78 [6], infectious bursal disease virus (IBDV) [7], infectious bronchitis virus (IBV) [8] and avian
79 influenza virus (AIV), which also poses a potential threat to human health [9]. Attempts to control
80 these viruses by vaccination or alleviate the impacts of disease have been utilised over the years
81 with varying degrees of success. Alongside improvement of vaccines and/or vaccine adjuvants
82 the identification of disease resistance genes can feed into conventional breeding programs, but
83 the selection of birds with improved innate immune responsiveness may result in a broader effect
84 than resistance to specific diseases [10,11]. Studies from MHC-congenic lines indicate that there
85 are MHC-related and non-MHC related factors involved in viral disease resistance. Research
86 using inbred/partially inbred chicken lines in response to viral disease has identified
87 transcriptomic variations either in the interferon genes or in their up- or downstream effectors
88 [12-15]. Given their role in the innate immune response and their variability in expression in
89 response to viruses, it is possible that genetic variants in the interferon pathways between
90 different chicken lines may contribute to resistant and susceptible phenotypes. Identifying
91 variants causative for susceptibility or resistance could therefore allow for the development of
92 breeding schemes to introduce viral resistance into commercial lines and also increase knowledge
93 of virus:host interactions.

94 The goal of the current *in silico* study was to identify genetic variants from whole genome
95 sequence data from 8 chicken research lines and to annotate these variants, i.e. to determine if
96 they are exonic, intronic, upstream or downstream of a gene. Functional prediction tools were
97 used to determine the impact of these variants. Finally, using prior knowledge of the lines'
98 susceptibility and resistance to IBV, IBDV, AIV and MDV, variants have been correlated to
99 disease response phenotype with the aim of identifying mutations potentially responsible for
100 specific resistance or susceptibility.

101

102 **Materials and Methods**

103 ***Determination of chicken line phenotype***

104 The **research** lines examined in this study were lines W1, 15I, 7₂, 6₁, C.B12, N, 0 and P2a
105 which have been previously described [12,16,17]. These are all White Leghorn lines inbred to
106 varying degrees. The level of inbreeding is indicated in **Supplementary File 1**. Lines 6₁, 7₂, 15I
107 and C are highly inbred (with inbreeding coefficients ranging from 0.72 to 0.85), while lines N,
108 P2a, and W1 are only partially inbred (with inbreeding coefficients ranging from 0.37 to 0.59).
109 Line 0, so called because it contains no avian leukosis virus subgroup E (ALVE) genes, was not
110 developed as an inbred line, but does show a low level in this study. Data from Kaiser et al. (2008)
111 was considered as a starting point for identifying line resistance and susceptibility phenotypes
112 [18]. However, these data were generated in the 1990s and contradictory findings have since been
113 identified [19,20]. A broad search of the literature was completed in order to classify lines as
114 either susceptible or resistant to each virus, as much as was possible. Studies of IBV [21-24],
115 IBDV [19,20,25,26], MDV [16,27,28] and AIV [29] infections were referenced.

116

117 ***Identification of chicken interferon genes of interest***

118 Ensembl genome browser release 103 (<https://www.ensembl.org/index.html>) was used to
119 identify the interferon pathway genes of interest and their genomic co-ordinates. Genomic
120 positions from this release were used for interrogating sequence data from the **research** lines
121 mapped to the GRCg6a chicken reference genome (GenBank assembly accession:
122 GCA_000002315.5). Paralogues with >95% target identity were also identified and examined in
123 this study [30].

124

125 ***Whole genome sequence data from the research lines***

126 Genomic data from the research lines is the same as that used in the development of the
127 600K chicken SNP genotyping array [31]. Briefly, ten chickens from each line were supplied by
128 the Institute of Animal Health (Compton, UK; now available through the NARF Edinburgh, UK),
129 with all chickens within lines being of the same gender (female in all lines except for male line
130 N chickens). DNA was extracted from blood samples and pooled for sequencing on an Illumina
131 GAIIX platform using a paired end protocol where read length was 101 bases. These previously
132 generated whole genome sequence data from each line were aligned to the GRCg6a chicken
133 reference genome using the Burrows-Wheeler Aligner mem (BWA-mem) software package,
134 version 0.7.15, using default settings [32].

135

136 ***Variant calling and annotation***

137 The Genome Analysis Toolkit (GATK) version 3.8 and Picard 2.9.2 packages were used
138 throughout the variant calling process following the best practices workflow for germline short
139 variant discovery [33]. Picard's SortSam function was used to sort the mapping data into
140 coordinate order and MarkDuplicates function highlighted duplicate reads. Base Quality Score
141 Recalibration (BQSR) of the mapped reads was then performed using the GATK. Over twenty
142 million known single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in the chicken genome from Ensembl
143 (release 92) were used in the BaseRecalibrator step as known variants to be masked from
144 considering as sequencing errors during the recalibration process. GATK's HaplotypeCaller
145 function was used to call short variants. This resulted in a GVCF file for each line, which were
146 then combined into one VCF file using the GenotypeGVCF function. The Variant Quality Score
147 Recalibration (VQSR) approach was applied for filtering variants [34]. For this, over one million
148 validated polymorphic SNPs [31] were used as a truth dataset alongside the previous known
149 dataset and the unfiltered variants from the research lines to create a trained Gaussian mixture

150 model using VariantRecalibrator. The model calculated a variant quality score log-odds
151 (VQSLOD) score for each SNP in the truth dataset and the research lines dataset.
152 ApplyRecalibration step of VQSR (also called “ApplyVQSR” in the latest version of the GATK)
153 was used with a sensitivity filter of 99% to remove SNPs with a VQSLOD score lower than the
154 top 99% of the truth set, as these are likely to be false positives. To further minimise the inclusion
155 of false positives, SNPs with a VQSLOD score <20 were removed.

156 The Ensembl variant effect predictor (VEP) webtool
157 (<https://www.ensembl.org/info/docs/tools/vep/index.html>) was used to annotate SNPs identified
158 within and around the genes of interest. Variants were defined as: upstream (if within 1 kb
159 upstream of transcription start site (TSS)), downstream (within 1 kb downstream of the gene), 3’
160 untranslated region (3’UTR), 5’ untranslated region (5’UTR), intronic, synonymous or missense
161 variants [35].

162

163 ***Prediction of potential functional impacts of SNPs***

164 To determine the potential impact of missense variants on protein function and amino acid
165 sequences, corresponding variants were examined using the Normal-SMART, SIFT-sequence,
166 PROVEAN protein and SNAP2 webtools. Normal-SMART (Simple Modular Architecture
167 Research Tool) (<http://smart.embl-heidelberg.de>) predicts domains within the protein sequence.
168 Variants affecting particular protein domains could therefore be identified [36]. SIFT-sequence
169 uses the SIFT (Sorting Intolerant From Tolerant) algorithm to predict whether an amino acid
170 substitution, due to a missense SNP, affects protein function based on sequence evolutionary
171 conservation and the physical properties of each amino acid. Default settings were used for the
172 prediction of SIFT score for each missense SNP [37]. Similarly, PROVEAN protein (Protein
173 Variation Effect Analyser) (http://provean.jcvi.org/seq_submit.php) is another method to
174 investigate the impact of amino acid substitution on the biological function of a protein [38] and

175 again the predictions were made using default settings. SNAP2 (Screening for Non-Acceptable
176 Polymorphisms; <https://roslab.org/services/snap2web/>) uses a neural network based classifier
177 for distinguishing between functional and neutral variants within protein sequence where the
178 prediction algorithm is trained using more than 100,000 experimentally annotated variants from
179 multiple online databases (PMD, SWISS-PROT, OMIM) and HumVar [39].

180 To determine potential impact of variants on micro-RNA (miRNA) binding sites, 3'UTR
181 variants were compared to miRNA binding sites identified via the miRDB
182 (<http://www.mirdb.org>) online database [40]. Potential impact of variants on transcription factor
183 binding sites (TFBS) was investigated by uploading 1kb of upstream gene sequences into the
184 MATCH 1.0 public webservice (<http://gene-regulation.com/pub/programs.html#match>). SNP
185 positions were compared to known TFBS and any changes recorded. Parameters used were: “high
186 quality matrices only” and to “minimise false positives” [41].

187 To determine the impact of variants on the mature mRNA secondary structure, SNPs
188 identified as 3'UTR, missense, synonymous and 5'UTR were analysed using the RNAsnp
189 (<https://rth.dk/resources/rnasnp/>) and SNPfold ([http://ribosnitch-
190 compute.bio.unc.edu/snpfold/SNPfold.html](http://ribosnitch-compute.bio.unc.edu/snpfold/SNPfold.html)) webtools alongside the mRNA sequence of the
191 affected gene of interest. RNAsnp assesses the effect of a SNP on RNA secondary structure, as
192 structural characteristics are essential for correct functioning of RNA molecules [42]. The
193 RNAsnp predictions were made using the ‘Mode 2’ function, which uses a local folding algorithm
194 designed for long RNA molecules. SNPfold considers all possible RNA conformations for the
195 input sequence and uses Pearson correlation coefficients to compare secondary structure change
196 between wild type and variant sequences [43]. The P-values indicating significance generated by
197 these software tools were corrected for multiple tests using Bonferroni correction.

198

199 **Results**

200 *Phenotype definition of chicken lines*

201 Previous observations of resistant and susceptible phenotypes in response to strains of IBV,
202 IBDV, MDV and AIV for the **research** lines investigated in this study are described in **Table 1**.
203 Resistance and susceptibility were determined based on variables such as viral titre, mortality,
204 clinical symptoms, and transmissibility. Issues encountered when considering such studies
205 included the subjective nature of how resistance and susceptibility are defined and the lack of
206 systematic study of these lines against the different viruses. These observations have also been
207 made at different time points of infection, different chicken ages and while using different virus
208 strains and infection dose or route, adding further complexity to an already complex trait. The
209 different MHC backgrounds of each line also need to be considered [12]. The phenotypes defined
210 were used to consider SNPs identified in the context of resistance and susceptibility depending
211 on how they distribute between lines.

212

213 *Chicken interferon pathway genes*

214 The genes of interest, the paralogues of these genes and their location in the GRCg6a
215 reference genome are shown in **Table 2**. Since the JAK-STAT pathway is intrinsic to ISG
216 regulation, the *TYK2*, *JAK1*, *JAK2*, *STAT1*, *STAT2* and *IRF9* genes were examined along with
217 the interferons and their receptors. Seventeen genes of interest were identified. *IFN α* and *IFN λ*
218 were found to have 11 and 3 paralogues respectively, resulting in 29 genomic locations being
219 explored. It should be noted that *IFN α* , *IFN β* , *IFN κ* and *JAK2* are all located on the Z sex
220 chromosome. In birds the female is the heterogametic sex, having ZW sex chromosomes, whereas
221 the male has two copies of the Z chromosome. Incomplete dosage compensation in chickens
222 results in higher expression of Z chromosome genes in males [44].

223

224 *SNPs across research lines identified in GRCg6a*

225 Prior to VQSR, 12,142,027 SNPs were identified between the GRCg6a reference genome
226 and the research lines. Over 81% of the SNPs (9,862,336) passed VQSR and 79% (9,584,464)
227 had a VQSLOD score >20. Of these, 1,760 were found to occur within the defined locations of
228 the genes of interest, including 1 kb up- and downstream of the genes. The distribution of these
229 SNPs after being defined by VEP can be seen in **Table 3**. The SNPs are split into the following
230 annotation categories: 81.4% (1,432) intronic, 5.74% (101) upstream, 5.17% (91) downstream,
231 2.95% (52) 3'UTR, 2.33% (41) synonymous, 2.05% (36) missense and 0.40% (7) 5'UTR SNPs.
232 Of the 29 genomic locations examined (**Table 2**), only 16 were found to contain one or more
233 SNPs when research lines were compared to the GRCg6a reference.

234 Only one of the *IFN α* paralogues contained SNPs, all of which were upstream of the gene.
235 *IFN λ* and its two paralogues were also not found to contain SNPs. It was considered that this may
236 be due to these genes being highly conserved. However, this finding prompted examination of
237 the sequence read depth of these genes in each line, and this identified low coverage for these
238 regions. For example, the *IFN λ* paralogue (*ENSGALG00000050947*) with the highest coverage
239 across all lines had an average read depth of only 1.55x. Compared to a longer gene with no
240 paralogues, such as *IFNARI*, the average read depth across lines was found to be 15x. Issues of
241 coverage observed are likely due to the presence of multiple similar paralogues in the genome
242 and the short length of reads (101 bp) used in this study, as this will result in failure to distinguish
243 unique genomic regions during read alignment. High GC content in particular regions will also
244 mean problems with sequence coverage. Given this finding and the importance of both *IFN α* and
245 *IFN λ* in these pathways it would be advisable to carry out long-read sequencing where reads can
246 cover the entire gene region, as this would allow unique reads to be mapped and variants to be
247 identified.

248 However, many more SNPs were detected in our current analysis using GRCg6a compared
249 to the previous analysis that used the Galgal4 reference genome [31]. The comparison is shown
250 in **Supplementary File 2**. The difference in the number reflects better assembly and more
251 complete build of GRCg6a, compared to Galgal4. For example, in Galgal4 no SNPs were
252 detected from genes on chr30 or 33 but in GRCg6a we detected many SNPs (e.g. from genes
253 TYK2 and STAT2). Moreover, in our current analysis we have applied a more advanced variant
254 calling approach (using GATK's VQSR method for filtration) compared to the hard filtration
255 applied in the previous analysis.

256

257 *Prediction of functional impacts of missense SNPs identified from genes of interest*

258 The potential functional consequences of identified missense SNPs (n=36) as predicted by
259 SIFT, PROVEAN and SNAP2 scores can be found in **Table 4**. Those predicted to have a
260 deleterious effect are shown in bold. A SIFT or PROVEAN score of less than 0.05 or -2.5
261 respectively, indicates a predicted deleterious change, whereas a SNAP2 score of greater than
262 zero predicts an impact on protein function. Thirteen of the amino acid substitutions were
263 predicted to have an effect by at least one of the webtools, with five of these being predicted by
264 two and the Y500D substitution in *JAK1* was predicted to have an effect by all three. The
265 locations of all 36 SNPs predicted protein domains impacted can be seen in **Figures 2A-K**.

266 Considering the different **research** lines, there are 42 instances where it could be inferred
267 a missense SNP contributes to resistance to one of the viruses, whereas 47 instances could be
268 related to susceptibility. The arguments for these can be found in **Supplementary File 3** (see
269 **worksheet: missenseSNPs**). For example, the aforementioned Y500D substitution, visible in
270 **Figure 2I**, occurs in lines C and W1 and affects the Normal-SMART predicted SH2 domain of
271 JAK1. It could be hypothesised that this SNP contributes to IBV resistance or AIV susceptibility
272 in line C, whereas in W1 it could be linked to IBDV susceptibility. Of the 36 SNPs, 13 were found

273 to be heterozygous. The remaining 23 SNPs were homozygous in at least one line. This finding
274 could have further implications as allele specific expression could potentially affect wild type vs
275 mutant protein function.

276

277 *SNPs potentially affecting mRNA secondary structure*

278 Twenty-one of the 136 SNPs occurring in the mRNA sequence among the lines were
279 predicted to affect mRNA secondary structure by at least one of the webtools (RNAsnp and/or
280 SNPfold with $P < 0.1$; **Table 5**). Only one SNP in the 3'UTR region of *IFN κ* (ChrZ:34,282,637)
281 was indicated to significantly impact secondary structure by both webtools. This SNP occurs in
282 AIV resistant line 0, but is absent from the susceptible C, therefore it could be perceived that this
283 variation affects the *IFN κ* mRNA in a way that may contribute to AIV resistance. In the context
284 of viral infection and how the SNPs distribute between the lines considered in this study, 31
285 instances of these could be related to viral resistance, whereas 21 instances could be related to
286 susceptibility (**Supplementary File 3; worksheet: mRNAstructureAlteringSNPs**).

287

288 *SNPs in micro-RNA and transcription factor binding sites potentially contribute to resistance* 289 *and susceptibility phenotypes.*

290 Three SNPs were found to impact either a TF or miRNA binding site, as listed in **Table 6**.
291 The gga-miR-1627-3p and gga-miR-196-1-3p binding sites in the 3'UTR of *IFNAR1* are seen to
292 be affected, while a V-MAF binding site upstream of *STAT1* is also disrupted. The miRNA gga-
293 miR-196-1-3p is believed to have multiple roles including embryonic development and feather
294 follicle development [45,46], whereas the V-MAF TF is a viral oncogene [47]. In the context of
295 viral infection and how the SNPs distribute between the lines, there are five instances where viral
296 resistance can be inferred, and two instances could be linked to susceptibility (**Supplementary**
297 **File 3, worksheet: TF-miRNA-bindingSNPs**). For example, the SNP upstream of *STAT1*

298 potentially affecting V-MAF binding occurs in the MDV resistant line 6₁ but is absent from the
299 susceptible lines 7₂ and 15I.

300

301 **Discussion**

302 Considering that the interferon pathways play a key role in immune responses, not only to
303 viral infections, but also bacterial and parasitic infections, it is plausible that variations in the
304 genes involved may contribute to differences in resistance and susceptibility. Here, we analysed
305 genome sequence data from 8 chicken **research** lines and identified variants from interferon
306 pathway genes. The impact of these SNPs was considered with regards their potential functional
307 effects and distribution amongst the lines. This process resulted in a total of 51 potentially
308 relevant SNPs being identified. When considered in terms of the impact of the SNP and in the
309 context of specific virus response, 78 instances could be related to resistance and 70 instances
310 could be related to susceptibility. **Table 7** highlights 19 SNPs of interest that correlate with
311 resistance or susceptibility to at least two of the viruses within the scope of this study.
312 Furthermore, prediction tools identified 5 of these 19 SNPs to have a significant impact on protein
313 function or mRNA folding.

314 It is possible to hypothesise the mechanism by which some of these SNPs may act given
315 their effect. Missense SNPs result in an amino acid change in the polypeptide sequence and this
316 may have consequences on the final protein structure, possibly affecting features such as substrate
317 binding efficiency, protein:protein complex interfaces or catalytic activity. The SNP at position
318 Chr30:182,787 where histidine is replaced by proline (H215P) lies in a predicted band 4.1 (B41)
319 domain of TYK2. This SNP is present in the IBV and MDV susceptible line 7₂ and the IBDV
320 susceptible line W1 and may be a contributing factor to these phenotypes. For example, the change
321 from the positively-charged, polar histidine to the neutral, non-polar proline may result in a
322 conformational change that negatively impacts the process of phosphorylation of the STAT

323 proteins, resulting in reduced overall upregulation of ISGs. This change could potentially explain
324 why line 7₂ developed more progressive MD compared to lines 151, 6₂ and N [27], or why greater
325 mortality was seen in line W1 chickens infected with IBDV compared with various other lines
326 [25].

327 The effect of a SNP on protein function can be executed not just by alteration of amino acid
328 but also by affecting the mRNA secondary structure. Exonic (both synonymous and missense),
329 5'UTR and 3'UTR SNPs may affect a transcript's secondary structure by altering base pairing
330 within the mRNA. Such structural alteration may affect mRNA stability. Altered secondary
331 structure around the 5'UTR region may impact translation initiation efficiency by affecting the
332 ability of the ribosome to bind to the mRNA, whereas secondary structure changes in the 3'UTR
333 region may affect accessibility of miRNAs to binding sites, impacting their ability to silence
334 translation in the mRNA [48,49]. In this study, a SNP at position Chr1:106,652,516 was identified
335 which results in a guanine to adenine change in the 3'UTR region of the *IFNGR2* mRNA in the
336 IBDV resistant line N and was predicted to significantly affect secondary structure. *IFNGR2*
337 exhibits greater levels of expression after infection with very virulent IBDV (vvIBDV) [20],
338 which would indicate the importance of this gene and the type II interferon pathway. It is possible
339 that this SNP in line N may synergise with this upregulation by preventing miRNA binding due
340 to altered secondary structure; leading to greater levels of translation and a greater type II pathway
341 response than compared to lines lacking this SNP, where miRNA binding and silencing may still
342 occur.

343 SNPs can also directly affect miRNA binding sites in the 3'UTR of the mRNA by altering
344 the recognition sequence, potentially impacting miRNA binding of the transcript and the resultant
345 silencing effect of this interaction. Using miRDB, it was seen that potential miRNA binding sites
346 for gga-miR-1627-3p and gga-miR-196-1-3p in the 3'UTR of *IFNARI* were altered by SNPs at
347 positions Chr1:106,632,281 and Chr1:106,631,586 respectively. *Gga-miR-1627-3p* was

348 previously found to exhibit greater expression in macrophages with the MHC haplotype B19
349 compared to those with B2, suggesting it may play a role in immune response [50]. The SNP
350 affecting the gga-miR-1627-3p binding site only occurs in line 0, which is perceived as resistant
351 to AIV, so it is therefore plausible that this SNP could contribute to this resistant phenotype.
352 Interferons were discovered due to their ability to inhibit influenza virus [51] and studies using
353 type I interferons as both a pre- treatment and treatment *in vitro* and *in vivo* have identified a
354 reduction in influenza virus replication [52,53]. Therefore, this SNP may reduce the silencing
355 effect of gga-miR-1627-3p binding, allowing greater IFNAR2 translation. Increased levels of
356 IFNAR2 at the cell surface could lead to a more responsive activation of the type I interferon
357 pathway upon influenza infection, resulting in a greater antiviral response.

358 Another example of a variant affecting a regulatory binding site was observed with the SNP
359 at position Chr7:7,933,106, just upstream of *STAT1*, where a base substitution is predicted in a
360 V-MAF TF binding site. V-MAF is an oncogene that was first identified in avian
361 musculoaponeurotic fibrosarcoma virus, however a V-MAF protein homolog (C-MAF) exists in
362 chickens, sharing 99.7% identity. It is likely that the chicken C-MAF will bind this same site,
363 with binding affected in lines 6₁, C, P2a and 0, altering *STAT1* expression in these lines. In
364 humans and mice, C-MAF has been shown to be involved in CD4 and CD8 T-cell subset
365 differentiation, function, and interleukin production [54,55]. Furthermore, research has indicated
366 that *C-MAF* expression is induced in a STAT1-dependent fashion in CD4⁺CD25⁻ T cells. It is
367 therefore possible that C-MAF binding at STAT1 could act as a self-upregulating positive
368 feedback loop [56]. *C-MAF* overexpression has been linked to T-cell lymphoma development in
369 both mice and humans [57] and a key outcome in MDV pathogenesis is the development of T-
370 cell lymphomas [58]. Interestingly, the SNP within the potential MAF binding site occurs in line
371 6₁ which is known for its resistance to MDV, but is absent in its susceptible counterpart, line 7₂.
372 Considering C-MAF's involvement in cancer development and potential regulation by STAT1,

373 this SNP may prevent C-MAF binding upstream of *STAT1*. The lack of binding may mitigate
374 carcinogenic effects that may be associated with upregulation of *STAT1*, leading to aberrant *C-*
375 *MAF* expression after MDV infection, and may explain the reduced pathogenesis and mortality
376 by MDV seen in line 6₁ [16].

377 Again, limitations on knowledge of TFBS and miRNA targets in chicken have to be
378 considered when these predictions are made. Fifty-two 3'UTR variants and 101 upstream variants
379 were identified in this study. Given the incomplete knowledge of miRNA and TF binding sites it
380 is possible that more of these variants than currently identified affect binding sites and potentially
381 contribute towards resistant and susceptible phenotypes.

382 In the current study, functional variants were mainly predicted from exonic, upstream and
383 UTR regions. However, such an approach fails to consider the potential impact of 81.4% of the
384 SNPs (1,432 intronic SNPs) in the studied regions. SNPs in intronic regions could potentially
385 impact splice sites, giving a different mRNA splice variant or by affecting splicing efficiency,
386 resulting in varying protein isoforms or expression levels which may affect phenotypes such as
387 disease resistance [59]. SNPs outside of genes can also affect expression by impacting distal
388 regulatory regions; TF binding at these sites may exist spatially close to promoter regions and
389 influence transcription initiation despite being distant in terms of genomic coordinate [60].

390 Also requiring further research is the impact of heterozygous SNPs. As shown in
391 **Supplementary File 1**, the vast majority of identified SNPs (78% to 95%) are homozygous.
392 However, the smaller proportion of heterozygous SNPs may represent accumulation of new
393 mutations over time, reflecting selective advantage (as being homozygous may have detrimental
394 consequence). Allele specific expression (ASE) of genes is the result of differential expression
395 occurring between the two parental alleles of one gene. This has implications in the context of
396 this study as several SNPs were found to occur in only one allele and therefore may be
397 upregulated or downregulated compared to the wild type allele. For example, the aforementioned

398 missense SNP at position Chr30:182,787 which results in a H215P substitution in the *TYK2* gene
399 is present in the MDV susceptible line 7₂ and absent from resistant line 6₁. The JAK/STAT
400 pathway has been previously found to contain SNPs exhibiting ASE in response to MDV [61]. It
401 is possible that SNPs occurring in alleles that experience greater expression upon infection may
402 have a significant effect on resistant or susceptible phenotypes. Considering the findings above,
403 MDV infection may result in greater H215P-TYK2 expression in line 7₂. This amino acid
404 substitution was predicted to be deleterious by PROVEAN and to affect protein function by
405 SNAP2. The increased levels of this affected TYK2 may result in less ISG induction leading to
406 greater viral replication and more severe infection.

407 The ultimate goal will be to breed for a more resilient bird that can tolerate and recover
408 from challenges without having lost productivity at the end of its rearing or laying period.
409 Previous work indicated that selection for production traits has resulted in weakened immunity
410 in commercial lines, but also suggested that selection for immunity was not detrimental to growth
411 [62]. Furthermore, a GWAS of indigenous African chickens found no correlation between
412 production traits and immunity traits [63]. Therefore, breeding schemes to introduce variants that
413 result in higher innate immune responsiveness may not negatively impact production. Another
414 economic advantage with using breeding schemes to introduce resilience is that this process does
415 not require gene-editing and will therefore not result in any consumer concerns over genetic
416 modification, however it will be a much slower process.

417 To enable breeding for more resilient birds we have to define the mechanisms of resistance,
418 as a variant conferring resistance to one virus could lead to susceptibility against another. The
419 observation that some SNPs appear to confer resistance in one line and susceptibility in another,
420 may be due to level of interferon response. For example, some viruses may require a more robust
421 response, which a particular SNP might yield, whilst with other viruses this more robust response
422 may give rise to the observed ‘susceptibility’. For some viruses, a particular IFN may be

423 detrimental and for others it won't because they have an ability to evade that response or to
424 downregulate and block the induction of the IFN response. Hence breeding for resistance to virus
425 A does not imply it will also impart resistance to virus B. Our study indicated that the SNP at
426 position Chr1:106,603,910 results in an R318K amino acid substitution in IL10R β . This SNP
427 may contribute to IBDV resistance in line C whilst it may also contribute to MDV susceptibility
428 in line 7₂. This SNP may enhance the type III interferon pathway's regulation of apoptosis [64]
429 which could therefore reduce bursal damage in IBDV infected birds due to aberrant apoptosis
430 [65] but may contribute to the development of lymphoma in MDV infected birds [66]. This
431 example indicates why unravelling the mechanism for resistance is of importance, as breeding
432 for variants at such loci may introduce susceptibility to other viruses outside the scope of this
433 study.

434 It is only possible to postulate the mechanism by which the SNPs identified in this study
435 function. Further research will be required to validate the effects of these variants on phenotype.
436 It is interesting to note that none of the examined genes are located on chromosome 16, so any
437 role in resistance/susceptibility is not due to co-selection with the MHC during inbreeding of
438 these lines. Furthermore, the current research is reductionist in considering only one SNP at a
439 time; resistance and susceptibility are polygenic traits where effects may only be measurable in
440 the presence of multiple SNPs working in concert with each other. Validation of candidate SNPs
441 predicted in this work could be achieved by introducing variants *in vitro*, *in ovo* and *in vivo* and
442 observing changes in anti-viral responses, while also ensuring that responses to other pathogens
443 are not negatively impacted. Our study further highlights the importance of the maintenance of
444 rare, inbred chicken lines, given that they may already contain loci for resistance and once these
445 have been identified a low-density SNP array could be developed to easily inform breeding
446 schemes.

447

448 **Conclusions**

449 In the interferon pathway genes studied, 1,760 SNPs were identified, of which 36 change
450 an amino acid, 21 were predicted to affect mRNA secondary structure and 3 to affect TF/miRNA
451 binding sites. Considering the research line phenotypes and the distribution of these SNPs, 78
452 instances could be related to resistance and 70 could be related to susceptibility to particular
453 viruses. Further research will be required to validate these SNPs and examine the mechanisms
454 involved in resistance or susceptibility. The current study has identified genomic variants in genes
455 in the interferon pathways of different chicken research lines. This pathway is an integral
456 component in innate immunity and can also contribute to the orchestration and development of
457 the adaptive immune response. Not only will these findings help explain host innate immune
458 responses and disease mechanisms used by these viruses and other micro-organisms, but it may
459 also assist in the identification of targets for selective breeding, drug design or vaccine
460 improvement. Eventually, this will pave the way for breeding programmes that result in more
461 robust commercial chicken lines.

462

463 **Author Contributions**

464 JM – carried out the analyses and wrote the manuscript supported by JS LV; AG – assisted with
465 genome mapping and variant calling; LV – conceived the project and provided immunology
466 advice; JS – conceived and supervised the project. All authors revised and approved the final
467 manuscript.

468

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470 For the purpose of open access, the author has applied a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY)
471 licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising from this submission.

472

473 **Data availability**

474 Genome sequence data are available in the European Nucleotide Archive under accession number
475 ERA11911030. All SNP information is provided in **Supplementary File 4.**

476

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484

485 **Conflict of Interest**

486 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
487 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

488

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693 **Supplementary Files**

694 **Supplementary File 1:** Summary of sequencing coverage, variant calling and line characteristics

695 **Supplementary File 2:** Comparison of the number of SNPs detected in GRCg6a and Galgal4
696 reference assemblies

697 **Supplementary File 3:** SNPs potentially conferring susceptibility/resistance, listed by disease

698 **Supplementary File 4:** SNPs identified in each studied gene as described by line

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719 **Tables**

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Table 1 - Resistant and Susceptible Phenotypes of **research lines**

Inbred Chicken Line	MHC B haplotype	Virus Resistance Phenotype (Resistant / Moderate Susceptibility / Susceptible)			
		IBV [21-24]	IBDV [19,20,25,26]	MDV [16,27,28]	LPAIV [29]
WI	B14	M	S	-	-
15I	B15	S	R	S	-
7₂	B2	S	R	S	-
6₁	B2	M	M	R	-
C	B4 and B12	R	R	-	S
N	B21	R	M	R	-
0	B21	-	R	-	R
P2a	B19	-	-	S	-

“R” denotes resistance, “M” denotes moderate susceptibility, “S” denotes susceptibility and “-” indicates no data identified.

These data do not account for potential gender differences.

These lines were originally housed at the Institute for Animal Health, Compton, UK, but are now available at the NARF, Roslin, UK

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Table 2 – Genes of interest identified in GRCg6a

Gene	Gene/Paralogue ID	Sequence Location and Direction
<i>IFNA</i>	ENSGALG00000052146	Chromosome 7: 4,610,682-4,612,191 forward strand
	ENSGALG00000050947	Chromosome 7: 4,572,389-4,573,897 forward strand
	ENSGALG00000047344	Chromosome 7: 4,591,535-4,593,042 forward strand
<i>IFNa</i>	ENSGALG00000048874	Chromosome Z: 7,395,233-7,395,995 forward strand
	ENSGALG00000052209	Chromosome Z: 7,410,282-7,411,044 forward strand
	ENSGALG00000044725	Chromosome Z: 7,399,231-7,399,942 forward strand
	ENSGALG00000047630	Chromosome Z: 7,381,503-7,382,265 forward strand
	ENSGALG00000050924	Chromosome Z: 7,401,271-7,402,033 forward strand
	ENSGALG00000053752	Chromosome Z: 7,387,284-7,388,046 forward strand
	ENSGALG00000054396	Chromosome Z: 7,385,475-7,386,237 forward strand
	ENSGALG00000046996	Chromosome Z: 7,377,531-7,378,293 forward strand
	ENSGALG00000053207	Chromosome Z: 7,414,251-7,415,013 forward strand
	ENSGALG00000054368	Chromosome Z: 7,391,261-7,392,023 forward strand
ENSGALG00000054104	Chromosome Z: 7,421,956-7,422,718 forward strand	
<i>IFNβ</i>	ENSGALG00000005759	Chromosome Z: 7,372,029-7,372,640 forward strand
<i>IFNκ</i>	ENSGALG00000015062	Chromosome Z: 34,282,011-34,285,224 reverse strand
<i>IFNγ</i>	ENSGALG00000009903	Chromosome 1: 35,173,604-35,177,772 reverse strand
<i>IFNAR1</i>	ENSGALG00000030363	Chromosome 1: 106,613,562-106,632,348 forward strand
<i>IFNAR2</i>	ENSGALG00000041867	Chromosome 1: 106,580,169-106,592,227 forward strand
<i>IFNLR1</i>	ENSGALG00000004231	Chromosome 23: 5,819,774-5,826,643 reverse strand
<i>IL-10Rβ</i>	ENSGALG00000037989	Chromosome 1: 106,593,970-106,604,799 forward strand
<i>IFNGR1</i>	ENSGALG00000013865	Chromosome 3: 54,895,190-54,914,161 forward strand
<i>IFNGR2</i>	ENSGALG00000032660	Chromosome 1: 106,645,075-106,653,536 forward strand
<i>TYK2</i>	ENSGALG00000030599	Chromosome 30: 178,603-197,548 forward strand
<i>JAK1</i>	ENSGALG00000011031	Chromosome 8: 28,552,333-28,603,383 reverse strand
<i>JAK2</i>	ENSGALG00000015027	Chromosome Z: 27,532,087-27,615,380 forward strand
<i>STAT1</i>	ENSGALG00000007651	Chromosome 7: 7,912,708-7,932,691 reverse strand
<i>STAT2</i>	ENSGALG00000030661	Chromosome 33: 6,934,615-6,940,207 forward strand
<i>IRF9</i>	ENSGALG00000030291	Chromosome 20: 10,063,682-10,066,572 reverse strand

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Table 3 – Distribution of SNPs in genes of interest across lines

Distribution of SNPs in genes of interest across lines									
Gene affected	Transcript ID	Total SNPs in gene (±1kb)	Upstream	Downstream	5'UTR	3'UTR	Intronic SNPs	Synonymous SNPs	Missense SNPs
<i>IFNγ</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000016105.4</i>	53	6	13	0	2	32	0	0
<i>IFNα</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000102661.1</i>	8*	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>IFNβ</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000039477.2</i>	10*	3	5	0	0	0	1	1
<i>IFNκ</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000032834.4</i>	9*	1	1	0	2	4	1	0
<i>IFNAR1</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000064880.2</i>	208	9	13	1	15	160	4	6
<i>IFNAR2</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000046822.2</i>	185	20	16	1	6	133	1	8
<i>IFNLR1</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000098112.1</i>	16	1	1	2	1	7	1	3
<i>IL-10Rβ</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000073701.2</i>	169	18	12	0	7	126	2	4
<i>IFNGR1</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000031776.5</i>	163	9	8	1	7	136	0	2
<i>IFNGR2</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000061931.2</i>	85	5	13	0	11	53	2	1
<i>TYK2</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000058693.2</i>	23	0	1	0	0	15	1	6
<i>JAK1</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000017969.6</i>	626	11	5	2	1	591	14	2
<i>JAK2</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000024235.6</i>	143	2	1	0	0	136	4	0
<i>STAT1</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000057169.2</i>	21	3	0	0	0	17	0	1
<i>STAT2</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000050242.2</i>	12	0	2	0	0	7	3	0
<i>IRF9</i>	<i>ENSGALT00000100907.1</i>	29	5	0	0	0	15	7	2
Total SNPs		1760	101	91	7	52	1432	41	36
SNP % distribution			5.74	5.17	0.398	2.95	81.4	2.33	2.05

*The low number of identified SNPs may be a reflection of the low sequence coverage in these regions

Table 4 - Missense SNPs in genes of interest identified in chicken lines

SNP Genome Coordinate	Protein affected	Line(s) in which SNP is present	Alleles (ref/SNP)	Amino acid substitution	SIFT score	PROVEAN score	SNAP2 score	Comments on SNP location
Chr1:106,613,646	IFNAR1	6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , 0	G/A	A4T	**0	0.012	-84	
Chr1:106,613,656	IFNAR1	7 ₂	C/T	A7V	**0	0.647	-25	
Chr1:106,621,892	IFNAR1	15I, 6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , C, N, P2a*, 0, WI	T/G	Y217D	0.29	0.363	32	Occurs in FN3 domain
Chr1:106,621,899	IFNAR1	N	A/G	E219G	0.44	-0.719	18	Occurs in FN3 domain
Chr1:106,623,894	IFNAR1	15I, 6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , C, N, 0, WI	G/A	S324N	1	1.099	-81	Occurs in tissue factor domain
Chr1:106,625,990	IFNAR1	0*	C/T	A404V	0.76	0.729	-87	Occurs in interferon binding domain
Chr1:106,587,598	IFNAR2	C	C/T	P45S	**0	0.759	-78	Occurs in tissue factor domain
Chr1:106,588,380	IFNAR2	15I, 7 ₂ , C, 0*, WI	C/T	H137Y	1	0.037	-65	
Chr1:106,588,700	IFNAR2	15I, 7 ₂ , P2a*, 0*, WI	A/G	N188D	0.7	-0.238	-89	Occurs in interferon binding domain
Chr1:106,589,401	IFNAR2	15I, P2a*, 0, WI	T/C	I214T	0.11	-0.435	-68	Occurs in interferon binding domain
Chr1:106,589,970	IFNAR2	15I, C, P2a*, 0*, WI	G/T	G264V	0.15	0.584	-1	Occurs in transmembrane region
Chr1:106,590,778	IFNAR2	15I, C, P2a*, 0, WI	A/G	I296V	1	-0.005	-75	
Chr1:106,591,040	IFNAR2	15I, C, P2a*, 0*, WI	G/A	G383D	0.69	1.243	-29	
Chr1:106,591,349	IFNAR2	15I, C, P2a*, 0, WI	C/T	T486M	**0	-0.991	-62	
Chr3:54,913,306	IFNGR1	15I, 6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , C, 0, WI	T/C	V395A	0.27	-0.16	-16	
Chr3:54,913,327	IFNGR1	15I, 6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , C, 0, WI	G/A	R402Q	0.48	1.272	-71	
Chr1:106,647,185	IFNGR2	6 ₁	T/C	C44R	0.62	3.391	-60	Occurs in tissue factor domain
Chr23:5,823,279	IFNLR1	N*	T/C	E151G	**0	-1.341	-19	Occurs in interferon binding domain
Chr23:5,822,624	IFNLR1	C*	A/G	S199P	0.23	-1.046	14	Occurs in interferon binding domain
Chr23:5,822,588	IFNLR1	7 ₂ *, C*, 0*	A/G	S211P	0.06	-4.218	41	Occurs in interferon binding domain
Chr1:106,602,130	IL10RB	6 ₁	T/G	S248A	1	0.375	-66	

Chr1:106,603,837	IL10RB	6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , N, P2a*, 0*	A/T	Q293H	0.04	-1.17	-95	
Chr1:106,603,910	IL10RB	7 ₂	A/G	R318G	0.38	-0.716	9	
Chr1:106,603,911	IL10RB	C, P2a*	G/A	R318K	1	-0.092	-78	
ChrZ:7,372,479	IFN β	N*	T/C	S151P	0.36	-1.728	52	Occurs in IFN α / β / δ domain
Chr7:7,923,855	STAT1	15I*, 7 ₂ *, WI*	A/C	V341G	**0.03	-4.766	39	Occurs in STAT binding domain
Chr8:28,566,979	JAK1	N*, P2a*, 0	A/G	V332A	0.67	-0.305	-67	
Chr8:28,564,446	JAK1	C*, WI*	A/C	Y500D	0.04	-3.757	61	Occurs in SH2 domain
Chr30:182,787	TYK2	7 ₂ *, WI*	A/C	H215P	0.2	-2.732	63	Occurs in B41 domain
Chr30:183,686	TYK2	15I*, 6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , N, P2a, 0, WI	G/A	R299Q	0.44	-0.551	-17	Occurs in B41 domain
Chr30:186,858	TYK2	7 ₂ *, C*, 0*	T/C	V550A	0.01	-2.65	-26	Occurs in SH2 domain
Chr30:190,505	TYK2	6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , P2a, 0*	G/A	S875N	0.45	0.351	-96	Occurs in TyrKc domain
Chr30:190,528	TYK2	C*	T/C	S883P	0.25	-3.994	12	Occurs in TyrKc domain
Chr30:190,801	TYK2	6 ₁ *	A/C	D908A	0.34	-1.029	-53	
Chr20:10,064,956	IRF9	P2a*	T/C	H186R	0.51	-1.24	-38	
Chr20:10,064,260	IRF9	6 ₁ *, C*, 0*	T/G	Y355S	0.15	-4.102	63	Occurs in IRF-3 domain

Scores in bold indicate a predicted significant effect

* SNP occurs in only one allele and is therefore heterozygous.

** SIFT scores with low confidence in the value due to too few comparable sequences for the software to make a reliable prediction

Table 5 - SNPs of interest predicted to potentially perturb mRNA secondary structure

SNP Genome Coordinate	mRNA affected	Line(s) in which SNP is present	Alleles (Ref/SNP)	mRNA base change	RNA _{snp} P-value	SNPfold P-value	Region Affected
Chr1:106,613,656	<i>IFNAR1</i>	7 ₂	C/T	C/U	0.4067	0.0078	Exonic
Chr1:106,622,867	<i>IFNAR1</i>	N, 0*	C/T	C/U	0.6077	#0.016	Exonic
Chr1:106,623,894	<i>IFNAR1</i>	15l, 6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , C, N, 0, WI	G/A	G/A	0.0446	0.4078	Exonic
Chr1:106,625,990	<i>IFNAR1</i>	0*	C/T	C/U	0.5257	0.0808	Exonic
Chr1:106,631,527	<i>IFNAR1</i>	P2a	G/A	G/A	0.8683	0.0086	3'UTR
Chr1:106,632,281	<i>IFNAR1</i>	15l, 6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , C, N, P2a*, 0 WI	T/C	U/C	0.9474	0.0093	3'UTR
Chr1:106,589,970	<i>IFNAR2</i>	15l, C, P2a*, 0*, WI	G/T	G/U	0.424	0.046	Exonic
Chr1:106,592,036	<i>IFNAR2</i>	15l, C, 0, WI	T/G	U/G	0.5046	0.0275	3'UTR
Chr3:54,913,306	<i>IFNGR1</i>	15l, 6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , C, 0, WI	T/C	U/C	0.084	0.3036	Exonic
Chr1:106,652,516	<i>IFNGR2</i>	N, 0*	G/A	G/A	0.9103	0.0198	3'UTR
Chr1:106,653,379	<i>IFNGR2</i>	N, 0*	C/T	C/U	0.1912	0.0473	3'UTR
Chr23:5,823,279	<i>IFNLR1</i>	N*	T/C	A/G	0.0811	0.3326	Exonic
Chr1:106,604,195	<i>IL10RB</i>	7 ₂ *, C*	T/G	U/G	0.045	0.2181	3'UTR
Chr1:106,604,577	<i>IL10RB</i>	15l, 0*, WI	G/A	G/A	0.0565	0.3225	3'UTR
ChrZ:34,282,637	<i>IFNK</i>	6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , N, P2a, 0, WI	C/T	G/A	#0.027	0.0968	3'UTR
Chr8:28,553,812	<i>JAK1</i>	15l, 7 ₂ , C, N*, P2a*	G/A	C/U	0.0978	0.591	Exonic
Chr8:28,559,109	<i>JAK1</i>	C	A/G	U/C	0.056	0.4255	Exonic
Chr8:28,564,450	<i>JAK1</i>	15l, 6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , C, N*, P2a*, WI	T/G	A/C	0.0972	0.4388	Exonic
Chr8:28,566,979	<i>JAK1</i>	N*, P2a*, 0	A/G	U/C	0.1547	0.0105	Exonic
Chr8:28,567,177	<i>JAK1</i>	P2a*	T/C	A/G	0.7025	0.0056	Exonic
Chr8:28,576,480	<i>JAK1</i>	N*, P2a*, 0	C/T	G/A	0.051	0.3395	Exonic

Allele changes are listed for the forward strand; *IFNLR1*, *IFNK* and *JAK1* are found on the reverse strand so the mRNA base changes observed in these genes reflect that of the template strand.

Scores in bold can be considered significant (P > 0.1), # - scores still significant after Bonferroni correction

* SNP occurs in only one allele and is therefore heterozygous.

Table 6 - SNPs of interest predicted to affect TF or miRNA binding sites

SNP Genome Coordinate	Gene/mRNA affected	Line(s) in which SNP is present	Alleles (Ref/SNP)	mRNA base change	Comments
Chr1:106,631,586	<i>IFNAR1</i>	0*	C/T	C/U	Identified as gga-miR-1627-3p binding site
Chr1:106,632,281	<i>IFNAR1</i>	15l, 6 ₁ , 7 ₂ , C, N, P2a*, 0, WI	T/C	U/C	Identified as gga-miR-196-1-3p binding site
Chr7:7,933,106	<i>STAT1</i>	6 ₁ , C, P2a*, 0*	C/T	N/A	Identified as V-MAF TF binding site

* SNP occurs in only one allele and is therefore heterozygous.

Table 7 – SNPs of interest correlating with resistance or susceptibility against more than one virus

SNP Genome Coordinate	Gene/mRNA affected	Phenotype (Resistant/Susceptible)	Virus affected (line with phenotype)	Comments
Chr1:106,603,837	<i>IL10RB</i>	Resistant	AIV (0) IBDV (7 ₂ , 15 ₁) MDV (N, 6 ₁)	Significant SIFT score of 0.04 Heterozygous in line 0
Chr1:106,621,899	<i>IFNAR1</i>	Resistant	IBV (N) MDV (N)	Significant SNAP2 score of 18
Chr1:106,622,867	<i>IFNAR1</i>	Resistant	AIV (0) IBDV (0) IBV (N) MDV (N)	SNPfold P-value = 0.016 – significant after Bonferroni correction for P < 0.1 Heterozygous in line 0
Chr1:106,625,990	<i>IFNAR1</i>	Resistant	AIV (0) IBDV (0)	SNPfold P-value = 0.0808 – not significant after applying Bonferroni correction Heterozygous in line 0
Chr1:106,652,516	<i>IFNGR2</i>	Resistant	AIV (0) IBDV (0) IBV (N) MDV (N)	SNPfold P-value = 0.0198 – not significant after applying Bonferroni correction Heterozygous in line 0
Chr1:106,653,379	<i>IFNGR2</i>	Resistant	AIV (0) IBDV (0) IBV (N) MDV (N)	SNPfold P-value = 0.0473 – not significant after applying Bonferroni correction Heterozygous in line 0
Chr23:5,823,279	<i>IFNLR1</i>	Resistant	IBV (N) MDV (N)	SNPfold P-value = 0.0811 – not significant after applying Bonferroni correction Heterozygous in line N
Chr8:28,566,979	<i>JAK1</i>	Resistant	IBDV (0) AIV (0) IBV (N)	SNPfold P-value = 0.0105 – not significant after applying Bonferroni correction Heterozygous in line N
Chr8:28,576,480	<i>JAK1</i>	Resistant	AIV (0) IBDV (0) IBV (N)	RNAseq P-value = 0.051 – not significant after applying Bonferroni correction Heterozygous in line N
ChrZ:7,372,479	<i>IFNβ</i>	Resistant	IBV (N) MDV (N)	Significant SNAP2 score of 52 Heterozygous in line N

Chr1:106,588,380	<i>IFNAR2</i>	Susceptible	MDV (15I, 7 ₂) AIV (C)	No impact calculated by functional prediction tools
Chr1:106,589,970	<i>IFNAR2</i>	Susceptible	MDV (15I, P2a) AIV (C) IBDV (WI)	SNPfold P-value = 0.046 – not significant after applying Bonferroni correction Heterozygous in line P2a
Chr1:106,590,778	<i>IFNAR2</i>	Susceptible	MDV (15I, P2a) IBDV (WI)	No impact calculated by functional prediction tools Heterozygous in line P2a
Chr1:106,591,040	<i>IFNAR2</i>	Susceptible	MDV (15I, P2a) AIV (C) IBDV (WI)	No impact calculated by functional prediction tools Heterozygous in line P2a
Chr1:106,591,349	<i>IFNAR2</i>	Susceptible	MDV (15I, P2a) IBDV (WI)	No impact calculated by functional prediction tools Heterozygous in line P2a
Chr1:106,592,036	<i>IFNAR2</i>	Susceptible	MDV (15I) IBDV (WI)	SNPfold P-value = 0.0275 – not significant after applying Bonferroni correction
Chr30:182,787	<i>TYK2</i>	Susceptible	IBV (7 ₂) MDV (7 ₂) IBDV (WI)	Significant PROVEAN score of -2.732 and significant SNAP2 score of 63 Heterozygous in lines 7 ₂ and WI
Chr7:7,923,855	<i>STAT1</i>	Susceptible	IBV (15I, 7 ₂) MDV (15I, 7 ₂) IBDV (WI)	Significant PROVEAN score of -4.766 and significant SNAP2 score of 39 Heterozygous in lines 15I, 7 ₂ and WI
Chr8:28,564,450	<i>JAK1</i>	Susceptible	AIV (C) IBDV (WI)	RNAseq P-value = 0.0972 – not significant after applying Bonferroni correction

Figure 1

Figure 1: The current model for the interferon response pathway of the chicken

Type I, II and III interferon molecules act as cytokines in a paracrine and autocrine fashion by interacting with the: IFNAR1:IFNAR2, IFNGR1:IFNGR2 and IFNLR1:IL-10R β dimeric receptor complexes respectively. Upon receptor binding, the Janus kinase (JAK) - signal transducer and activation of transcription (STAT) pathway is activated, whereby phosphorylation of STAT1 and STAT2 causes them to dimerise. In mammals this dimer then goes on to form the complex interferon stimulated gene factor 3 (ISGF3 - in mammals this complex forms via interactions with IRF9, * however a chicken orthologue of this protein has yet to be identified). The ISGF3 complex can then enter the nucleus and bind to interferon stimulated response element (ISRE) sequences resulting in the upregulation of hundreds of ISGs and a specific antiviral state. In the case of the type II system: STAT1 and STAT2 form a homodimer that can then enter the nucleus and bind to gamma-activated sequences (GAS) resulting in upregulation of specific ISGs [2,3]. This image was created using modified images from Servier Medical Art, licensed under a Creative Common Attribution 3.0 Generic License. <http://smart.servier.com>

Figure 2

Figure 2 - Location of missense SNPs with regards to predicted protein domains

(A) IFNAR1 - Y217, E219G and A404V can be found in fibronectin type 3 (FN3) domains. (B) IFNAR2 - P45S occurs in a tissue factor domain, N188D and I214T occurs in an interferon binding domain and G264V occurs in the transmembrane region. (C) IFNGR1 - No SNPs were identified in the predicted domains. (D) IFNGR2 - C44R in tissue factor domain. (E) IFNLR1 - E151G, S199P and S211P occur in an interferon binding domain. (F) IL10R β - No SNPs were identified in predicted domains. (G) IFN β - S151P SNP in IFN $\alpha/\beta/\delta$ domain. (H) STAT1 - V341G SNP in STAT binding domain. (I) JAK1 - Y500D occurs in an Src Homolog 2 (SH2) domain. (J) TYK2 - H215P and R299Q occur in a band 4.1 (B41) domain and S875N, S883P and D908A occur in tyrosine kinase catalytic domains (TyrKc). (K) IRF9 - Y335S occurs in an interferon regulatory factor 3 (IRF3) domain. NB. Chicken lack IRF3 but have an IRF7 orthologue. Legend: IF $\alpha\beta\delta$ - Interferon alpha, beta and delta domain; STAT_int - STAT protein interaction domain; STAT_alpha - STAT protein all-alpha domain; STAT_bind - STAT protein DNA binding domain; B41 - band 4.1 homologue domain (also known as ERM domain - erzin/radixin/moesin domain); STYKc - protein kinase of unclassified specificity; IRF - interferon regulatory factor domain. Pink indicates low complexity regions and dark blue blocks signify transmembrane regions.